
CLUTCH SIZE, MORPHOLOGY AND HATCHING TIME OF *KENTROPYX CALCARATA* (SQUAMATA: TEIIDAE) FROM ATLANTIC FOREST: A CASE REPORT

Tamanho da ninhada, morfologia e tempo de eclosão de *Kentropyx calcarata* (SQUAMATA: TEIIDAE) da Mata Atlântica: Um relato de caso

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ABSTRACT

Reproductive traits (i.e. clutch size, newborn size, age at reproduction, reproductive effort and behavior) is a key life-history trait, with direct consequences on physical fitness. The objective of this work was provided data about the clutch size, the incubation time of a pregnant female and the incubation four eggs in the laboratory, as well as morphological data and behavior of the newly hatched of *Kentropyx calcarata* from an individual captured in the wild in the Atlantic Forest biome in the northeast from Brazil. Clutch size was similar to that described for individuals from the Amazon rainforest and cerrado enclaves in the Amazon; the hatchlings were slightly smaller in size than those described for the Amazon forest and relatively similar as the Atlantic Forest.

Key-words: Clutch size, Incubation time, Life history.

RESUMO

As características reprodutivas (i.e. tamanho da ninhada, tamanho do recém-nascido, idade de reprodução, esforço reprodutivo e comportamento) são atributos fundamentais da história de vida que apresentam consequências diretas na aptidão física dos indivíduos. O objetivo deste trabalho foi fornecer dados sobre o tamanho da ninhada, tempo de incubação de uma fêmea grávida e a incubação de quatro ovos em laboratório, além de dados morfológicos e de comportamento dos recém-eclodidos de *Kentropyx calcarata* através de um indivíduo capturado em ambiente selvagem no bioma Mata Atlântica no nordeste do Brasil. O tamanho da ninhada foi semelhante ao descrito para indivíduos da Floresta Amazônica e enclaves de Cerrado na Amazônia; os recém eclodidos apresentaram-se ligeiramente menores que os descritos para a floresta amazônica e relativamente semelhantes aos de Mata Atlântica.

Palavras-chave: Tamanho da ninhada, Tempo de incubação, História natural.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Lizards in nature deal with different biotic and abiotic pressures that can affect their reproductive cycles and require the use of different life history tactics (FITCH, 1970; ROFF, 1992; 2002; WERNECK *et al.*, 2009; VITT, 2013; MESQUITA *et al.*, 2016). These variations in life history traits are exhibited through changes in lifespan, reproductive frequency, and the number and size of offspring (BROWN; SHINE, 2006; WERNECK *et al.*, 2009; ALONZO; KINDSVATER, 2008; Vitt, 2013; MARQUES *et al.*, 2021).

Thus, quantitative data on reproductive traits such as incubation time, clutch size, egg mass and volume, and body size are strategic for understanding different aspects of life history and evolution of these individuals (LACK, 1947; STEARNS, 1992; GARLAND *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, this information allows us to infer about the ecology of these reptiles through the understanding of how energy is allocated for reproduction and how the trade-offs between litter size and number correlate (PIANKA; VITT, 2003; WERNECK *et al.*, 2009; LANTYER-SILVA *et al.*, 2012; VITT, 2013; MESQUITA *et al.*, 2016).

Kentropyx calcarata (Spix, 1825) is the most widely distributed species of its genus, occurring in several South American countries (GALLAGHER *et al.*, 1986; ÁVILA-PIRES, 1995). In Brazil, its populations can be found in Amazon Forest (VITT, 1991; VITT *et al.*, 1997), Atlantic Forest (GALLAGHER *et al.*, 1986; LANTYER-SILVA *et al.*, 2012; FILADELFO *et al.*, 2013; FRANZINI *et al.*, 2019; VIEIRA, 2018; VIEIRA *et al.*, 2023a, 2023b), Cerrado (VITT, 1991; ÁVILA-PIRES, 1995; ÁVILA-PIRES *et al.*, 2012), Mangroves (ROBERTO *et al.*, 2012), Restinga (TEIXEIRA, 2001; COUTO-FERREIRA *et al.*, 2011), transition sites between Cerrado and Amazon Forest (ÁVILA; KAWASHITA-RIBEIRO, 2011), Mountain Forest Relics (known as “Brejos de Altitude”) (BORGES-NOJOSA; CARAMASCHI, 2003) and in urban areas (OLIVEIRA *et al.*, 2016; MATOS-SANTOS *et al.*, 2021).

These lizards are characterized by being diurnal, heliothermic, terrestrial and active foragers (VITT, 1991; VITT *et al.*, 1997; LIMA *et al.*, 2001; FRANZINI *et al.*, 2019; VIEIRA, 2018; VIEIRA *et al.*, 2023a, 2023b), which are usually associated to microhabitats with leaf litter, fallen logs, tree roots, natural and artificial clearings, forest edges and riparian vegetation near water bodies (VITT, 1991; VITT *et al.*, 1997; SILVEIRA; AZEVEDO-RAMOS, 2010; FRANZINI *et al.*, 2019; VIEIRA, 2018; VIEIRA *et al.*, 2023a, 2023b). They are oviparous and clutches are in general from about three to ten eggs (VITT, 1991; LANTYER-SILVA *et al.*, 2012; FILADELFO *et al.*, 2013; WERNECK *et al.*, 2009), that can be buried in the soil (VITT, 1991), inside decomposing logs (MAGNUSSON;

LIMA, 1984), whorls and canopy of bromeliads (LANTYER-SILVA *et al.*, 2012; MATOS-SANTOS *et al.*, 2021).

Reports on incubation time, clutch size, egg mass and volume, and body size of *K. calcarata* are available from the Amazon Forest and the Atlantic Forest, in particular related to data regarding eggs found in communal nests or occasional reports of biology and behavior (MAGNUSSON; LIMA, 1984; VITT, 1991; LANTYER-SILVA *et al.*, 2012; FILADELFO *et al.*, 2013; FRANZINI *et al.*, 2019; MATOS-SANTOS *et al.*, 2021). However, data on the incubation time of a pregnant female and on the behavior of newly hatched females is still scarce in the literature. With this, our objective was to describe the size of the clutch, the gestation period and the incubation time of the eggs, in addition to morphology of the newborns and describing the hatching behavior through the observation of a female of *Kentropyx calcarata* from a fragment of Atlantic Forest biome of northeastern Brazil. Finally, we compare our observations with those found in the literature, including for cogenetic species.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study area: The collection was carried out at SEMA II (6°42'36"S and 35°10'38"W) of the Reserva Biológica Guaribas (ICMBIO, 2003) located in the municipality of Mamanguape, state of Paraíba, Brazil (Figure 1) (VIEIRA *et al.*, 2023a). The climate is characterized according to the Köppen system as rainy tropical, with average annual temperature varying between 24° and 26°C (KOPPEN; GEIGER, 1936; ICMBIO, 2003), with the hottest months being december and february, with high average temperatures of between 28° and 30° C. The rainy season begins in February and ends in July, the average annual precipitation is 1634.2 mm (ICMBIO, 2003; MME, 2005; MELO; VIEIRA, 2017). The region comprises evergreen forest type, with most of the area formed by semi-deciduous forest, characterized by primary vegetation with large and medium-sized trees (ICMBIO, 2003).

Figure 1 - Map of the study area, at SEMA II of the Reserva Biológica Guaribas, in Mamanguape, state of Paraíba (PB).

Source: Vieira (2018).

2.2 Analysis and deposit of matéria

On 24 April 2017, was doing fieldwork at the SEMA II of Reserva Biológica Guaribas ($06^{\circ}42'36''$ S and $35^{\circ}10'38''$ W) in municipality of Mamanguape, Paraíba state, northeastern of Brazil, and we captured an adult female of *K. calcarata*. We identified that the individual contained oviductal eggs after manual palpation. The specimen was transported to the laboratory at the Universidade Estadual da Paraíba (UEPB) (Collection permits No. 48256-1 by Ministério do Meio Ambiente/Instituto Chico Mendes de Conservação da Biodiversidade/SISBIO), was conditioned in a terrarium (plastic box) that simulated the natural habitat of *K. calcarata*, with dry and decomposing logs, leaves, rocks, sand and water (ad libitum) (Figure 2A), which was maintained at ambient temperature and humidity, the lizard was not handled or disturbed except for water change. The specimen was feed with crickets, cockroaches and beetles.

To avoid disturbances, we measured the snout vent length (SVL) with a digital caliper (0.1 mm precision) and its body mass with a digital scale (0.01 g precision) after oviposition. The female measured 91.98 mm SVL, and weighed 26.4 g mass. As soon as oviposition occurred, the eggs were

individually labeled with a hydrographic pen, they were all together, side by side (but not pinned), in a hole two centimeters from the soil surface (Figure 2B). We carefully handled the egg and measured its mass using a digital caliper.

Figure 2 - Female of *K. calcarata* (A) and the egg laying site (B) in the terrarium.

Source: Own authorship (2017).

After the measurements, we returned the eggs to the terrarium, keeping the female in the same room, and we monitored the temperature and humidity of the air inside the container every day, using a digital thermo-hygrometer DRS. We follow the monitoring three times a day, now checking the eggs for signs of hatching (cracks in the egg shell) (GUTZKE *et al.*, 1984).

After oviposition of the female and completion of hatching of the newborns, we killed the specimens with an intracelomic injection of Lidocaine Hydrochloride (2%), fixed in formalin (10%) (HACC, 2004; Conselho Federal de Biologia, 2012), and deposited in the Coleção de Referência do Laboratório de Herpetologia at Universidade Estadual da Paraíba. For each lizard, we recorded the body mass, snout–vent length (SVL), and head length (HL). To determine the sex of the specimens, we dissected the lizards and examined the gonads, checking hemipenis and presence of testicles in males, and ovaries in females. We estimated the eggs volume using the ellipsoid formula (MAGNUSSON *et al.*, 2003): where V = volume, L = length and W = width; $\pi = 3.14$ (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - Ellipsoid formula.

$$V = \frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{length}{2} \right)^2 \left(\frac{width}{2} \right)$$

Source: Vieira (2018).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We checked the terrarium three times a day, about 110 days straight after the female was collected, until on the afternoon of August 12, 2017, when we dug the terrarium soil, we found an oviposition site with eggs. Offspring started hatching on 3 October 2017, after 53 days of incubation, while from the capture of the pregnant female in the field until the first hatchings was 162 days. The mean air temperature and humidity during the incubation were 28.4 °C (varying between 26.1–29 °C) and 86% (82–89%), respectively.

As for the incubation period from oviposition observed in *K. calcarata*, our results were similar to the interval observed by Vitt (1991), who after collecting eggs in communal nests, the period until hatching was between 56-83 days, and longer than that observed by Filadelfo *et al.* (2013) who recorded 49 days. Compared to cogenetic species, the egg incubation period was similar to that of the approximately three months observed in *Kentropyx lagartija* (Gallardo, 1962) (TULLI; SCROCCHI, 2005). When considering the entire period from collection to first hatching, our results are slightly higher than those found by Rojas *et al.* (2016) for *Kentropyx altamazonica* (Cope, 1875).

Seven eggs were laid, three of them were already damaged and broken. The four eggs' average length and width were 14.06 mm and 11.05 mm, respectively. Hatchlings mean SVL was 33.63 (range: 31.52–35.06 mm); body mass was 1.45 g (1.1–1.8 g) (Table 1). The eggs were oval, quite fragile and leathery, white with yellow spots as reported by Lantyer-Silva *et al.* (2012) and Filadelfo *et al.* (2013).

Table 1 - Data about eggs and hatchlings of *K. calcarata* from Atlantic Forest, northeastern Brazil. EM = egg mass, EL = egg length, EW = egg width, EV = egg volume, SVL = snout-vent length, HL = head length.

Individual	Hatching date	Incubation time (days)	Sex	EM (g)	EL (mm)	EW (mm)	EV (mm ³)	Mass (g)	SVL (mm)	HL (mm)
RVSV 1	03 Oct 2017	53	F	2.10	17.12	13.14	1546.93	1.8	35.06	6.8
RVSV 2	05 Oct 2017	55	M	1.98	16.97	12.69	1430.15	1.7	34.09	6.5
RVSV 3	05 Oct 2017	55	F	1.51	12.82	10.77	778.21	1.2	31.52	6.1
RVSV 4	05 Oct 2017	55	M	1.33	9.36	7.46	272.59	1.1	33.86	6.7
Mean				1.73	14.06	11.05	1006.9	1.45	33.63	6.52

Source: Research data (2023)

In our study, the female of *K. calcarata* deposited seven eggs in the terrarium, the overall clutch size ranged from 3 to 10 eggs (average: 5.63± 1.23 eggs) (VITT, 1991; WERNECK *et al.*, 2009; LANTYER-SILVA *et al.*, 2012). Similar to our observation, Franzini *et al.* (2019) reported clutch sizes of 5–9 eggs for *K. calcarata* from the Atlantic forest in Paraíba state; found reproductive females throughout the year and specimens containing eggs in the oviduct in 6 months of the year..

The eggs mass recorded in our study (Table. 1) is smaller than those observed by Vitt (1991) ($4.059 \pm 0,02$ g) on Amazonian Forest, as well relatively smaller than recorded by Filadelfo et al., (2013) (2.0 ± 0.06 g, range = 1.9–2.1 g). Lantyer-Silva *et al.* (2012) weighed two egg layings in an area of the Atlantic Forest of Bahia. The first, made up of three eggs, weighed much more than ours; however, the second set, consisting of four eggs, weighed well below that verified by us. As well Lantyer-Silva *et al.* (2012) we believe this may indicate differences related to the biotic and regional conditions of each location. Compared to cogeneric species, these data are only available for *K. lagartija*, and the egg weight (1.84 ± 0.22) (TULLI; SCROCCHI, 2005) was close to that observed by us in this work.

Our results about length and width of eggs are smaller to that recorded by Filadelfo *et al.* (2013) (length = 18.7 ± 0.6 mm, range = 17.3–19.7 mm, width = 13.4 ± 0.9 mm, range = 12.0–14.9) and Matos-Silva *et al.* (2021) (18.11 ± 1.20 mm), as well Vitt (1991) (length = 18.5 ± 0.21 mm, width = 9.7 ± 0.17 mm), although Vitt (1991) found much larger eggs in nests (length = 23.85 ± 0.36 mm, range 22.9–24.6 mm, width = 17.08 ± 0.15 mm, range 16.8–17.5 mm). However, the length we recorded was well above that observed by Werneck *et al.* (2009). Regarding the cogeneric species, the length was very similar to that observed in *K. altamazonica* (ROJAS *et al.*, 2016).

The volume of eggs, was lower than observed by Lantyer-Silva *et al.* (2012) (1592.61 ± 671.12 mm³, range = 1145.87–2591.82 mm³) for eggs incubated in bromelians at Atlantic Forest, which even has the largest volume record of an egg of *K. calcarata*. Our record is superior to that observed by Franzini *et al.* (2019) in the Atlantic Forest of Paraíba, where the average volume of eggs was 360.93–610.95 mm³, and is similar to Vitt (1991) (0.921 ± 0.031 mm³) and Werneck *et al.* (2009) (921 ± 149.13 mm³) in Amazon Forest.

In Squamata, as observed by Werneck *et al.* (2009), there is often a trade-off relationship between the size and body mass of the female and the body size of the offspring and its mass, due to the volume of the egg and amount of yolk that will influence the size of the neonates (VITT; PRICE, 1982). The body size of hatchlings were similar to Vitt (1991) (SVL = 34.05 ± 0.05 , range = 32–35 mm) and Filadelfo *et al.* (2013) (SVL = 33.0 ± 2.1 mm, range = 30–36 mm), being smaller than observed by Lantyer-Silva *et al.* (2012) (SVL = 36.01 ± 1.19), and similar to cogeneric species like *K. altamazonica* (ROJAS *et al.*, 2016) (SVL = 33.07 ± 0.0) and *Kentropyx viridistriga* (Boulenger, 1894) (SVL = 32.2, 33.6 and 33.7 mm) (ORTIZ *et al.*, 2016), larger than those recorder of *K. lagartija* (SVL = 9.9 ± 1.5 mm) (TULLI; SCROCCHI, 2005).

The mass of hatchlings registered by us is quite similar to the records for *K. calcarata* by

Lantyer-Silva *et al.* (2012) (1.02 ± 0.09 g) and Filadelfo *et al.* (2013) (1.04 ± 0.05 g) in Atlantic Forest, and by Vitt (1991) (0.989 ± 0.18 g) in Amazon Forest. The congeneric species with registers of weight in the literature show up smaller *K. lagartija* (0.72 ± 0.11 g) (TULLI; SCROCCHI, 2005) and *K. altamazonica* (0.8 ± 0.0 g) (ROJAS *et al.*, 2016), when compared to *K. calcarata*.

We observed the birth of four lizards, the neonates moved vertiginously inside the egg, emerging through the distal region, forcing the shell until the rostral portion of the head emerged, making it possible to observe the nostrils, and soon after the whole head and eyes, possibly with the help of the muzzle. The very structure of the eggs were used to leverage the body out of the shell, as they emerge from the eggs, the lizards extend their tongue slowly, inspecting the environment, and no longer return to the eggs. During hatching, we observed that no individual came out of the egg at the same time as another emerged, including those who checked an individual with its head sticking out.

Immediately after full hatching, the individuals showed quite independent behavior. They are quite active, they move quickly in the sand exploring the environment and, at the slightest disturbance, they hide, generally under the litter and trunks. We did not observe any type of interaction or care by the female after hatching.

4. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In this study, we expand the general data on the reproductive biology of *Kentropyx calcarata* in the Brazilian Atlantic Forest, which helps to understand in particular the reproductive cycles of the species in this biome, and how females use their energy for reproduction, and thus, indirectly contributes to knowledge of the conservation status of the species through the relationships between egg, clutch and female size, as well as the success of hatching and the survival of females and newborns. Finally, we report for the first time the gestation period of a *K. calcarata* female and the behavior of the newborns.

However, we make the caveat that we cannot disregard the limitations of our data and the literature itself (ie with regard to the duration of pregnancy, the behavior of newborns, parental care, among others). Therefore, studies with a larger sample size are still needed to expand the understanding of the reproductive biology of *K. calcarata*, but also to analyze the influence of other factors on litter size such as reproductive quality of the adult, stress levels, and type of feeding, and which, in short, can be associated with the conditions of captivity themselves.

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